

Supplementary Materials: Open and Axial Coding for HOW E-COMMERCE INFLUENCES LAST-MILE PRACTICES THAT FOSTER INFORMALITY

This document presents supplementary materials for the study titled "*HOW E-COMMERCE INFLUENCES LAST-MILE PRACTICES THAT FOSTER INFORMALITY*", which has been accepted for presentation at CityLogistics 2025 (Conference ID: 1080). The study examines the role of informality in last-mile logistics within e-commerce operations, highlighting its impact on labor conditions, road safety, and regulatory frameworks.

The document consists of two sections:

1. Open Coding labels: A complete list of meaningful units identified during the first phase of analysis.
2. Axial Coding framework: A graphical representation of how these codes were grouped into broader analytical categories, illustrating the structural role of informality in last-mile logistics.

These materials aim to enhance transparency and replicability in qualitative research. For a detailed discussion and interpretation of these findings, refer to the full paper presented at *CityLogistics 2025*.

Open Coding Labels

In this phase, the interviews were analyzed through Open Coding, where transcripts were broken down into meaningful units to identify emerging key concepts. The following list presents all identified codes, reflecting the diverse factors influencing last-mile logistics in e-commerce.:

Increased exposure	Institutional disconnect
Lack of personal protective equipment usage	Lack of enforcement
Increased circulation speed	Reduced state revenue
Non-compliance with traffic regulations	Lack of e-commerce characterization
Driver fatigue	Disinterest among ministries
Lack of vehicle maintenance	Local government limitations
Driving under adverse conditions	Fear of political capital loss
Substance abuse	Reduced fiscal capacity
Driver distraction	Market dynamics velocity
Risky driving behavior	Business lobbying and associations
Damage to road infrastructure	Absence of public initiatives
Loss of human lives	Tax evasion
Permanent injuries	Lack of operational data
Medical care through mandatory accident insurance (SOAT)	Rights acquired through informality institutionalization
Administrative costs for traffic incident management	Poor road infrastructure
Delivery time pressure	Absence of parking management
Absence of physical workspaces	No restrictions on heavy vehicles in residential areas
No vehicle insurance	Lack of territorial planning
No life insurance	No establishment of loading and unloading zones
Lack of training	Lack of traffic control
Non-payment of social security contributions	Earnings allocated to current consumption
Lack of company support	Survival-driven production
Mandatory employee-funded equipment	Payment per task
Severity of penalties	Preference for motorcycle use
Extended working hours	Unregulated and uncompetitive market
Social undervaluation	Ease of job placement
Work under adverse conditions	Preference for informality
Perception of insecurity regarding theft	Independence
Disconnect between companies and drivers	Versatile work schedules
Workers outside the pension system	High wages
Subsidized healthcare-based social security	Job scarcity
Lack of determination	Immigrants
Insufficient existing regulation	State inefficiency and distortions
Absence of specific regulation	Technological integration
	Digital transport applications
	Big Data
	APIs

Blockchain
Digital marketing
Operational optimization
Trend to reduce delivery times
Logistics cost reduction
Inventory management
Implementation of urban micro-hubs
Process automation
Fleet management
Route optimization
Transport logistics
Outsourcing last-mile deliveries with informal workers
Transport and logistics companies
E-commerce companies
Detachment from logistics processes
Informality as a competitive advantage
Labor subordination to maintain profitability
Delivery platforms
Delivery time/bonus incentives
Ranking systems among delivery drivers
Support for new informal markets
Motorcycle rentals
“Ghost kitchens”
Delivery time/bonus incentives
Transition to a hub-and-spoke model

10-minute deliveries within a 2 km radius
Sustainability-related practices
Limited sustainable practices
Delegation of social and environmental responsibility
Lack of consideration for social costs in route optimization
Increased demand for delivery drivers
Tendency to avoid order consolidation
Lack of civil responsibility
Trust in e-commerce
Perception of insecurity towards delivery drivers
Expectation of cost and time reduction
Barriers to eco-friendly fleet adoption
Increase in emissions
Noise pollution
Limited sustainable practices
Negative impacts on quality of life
Public space appropriation by delivery drivers
Use of traditional vehicles
Lack of incentives and funding
No standardization of bicycles as cargo vehicles
Energy uncertainty

